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Department of Computer Science & Engineering

Vision

To be a center of excellence in providing globally standard education and training in the field of Computer Science & Engineering for producing competent and responsible professionals.

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To prepare students for successful careers and lifelong learning in Computer Science & Engineering while inculcating professional behavior, strong ethical values and leadership abilities in them.